

The Influence of South Korean Films on the Appearance of Food in Indonesia in 2017-2024

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the influence of South Korean films and dramas on the variety of Korean food in Indonesia since 2016. Korean food in K-dramas and K-films not only complements the story but also shapes consumer interest in Indonesia. The author employs the concept of gastrodiploamacy to illustrate the application of popular media in cultural promotion. The results show that Korean restaurants in Indonesia have begun to adapt their food service to match what is displayed on screen, including the use of metal cutlery and banchan. Local factors such as halal certification and taste adjustments are also important in attracting Indonesian consumers. This study confirms that popular culture can influence consumption trends and create opportunities for cross-border culinary businesses.

KEYWORDS: Gastrodiploamacy, Food, Korean Wave, Indonesia, Film

I. INTRODUCTION

South Korea has successfully leveraged its cultural influence as a diplomatic tool through a global phenomenon known as the Korean Wave, or K-Wave. This encompasses the global spread of South Korean popular culture, including music (K-pop), dramas (K-Drama), and films, known as Hallyu. In 2016, the influence of South Korean films and dramas on food presentation in Indonesia grew in popularity. The appetizing visualization of traditional Korean food in various film and drama scenes influenced the way food was served in Korean restaurants in Indonesia. This includes table settings, the use of typical Korean cutlery, and the presentation of dishes that resemble those depicted in Korean media. According to (Wachyuni, 2023), the visualization of food in Korean dramas appeals to viewers, encouraging them to seek out culinary experiences at local restaurants.

The global popularity of K-pop, Korean films, and dramas has increased interest in Korean culture, including its food. Korean food is not only part of popular culture but also reflects the unique historical and geographical values of the Korean Peninsula. Many misconceptions arise from the dominance of Chinese historical narratives, which misunderstand the identity of K-food. Korean food developed in geographical isolation, utilizing local ingredients such as cabbage, soybeans, and chili peppers through fermentation to create Kimchi and Jang.

(Kwon, 2023)

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This is supported by South Korea's gastrodiplomacy strategy, which promotes culinary culture through popular media. Korean restaurants in Indonesia adapt their food presentation to consumer expectations influenced by Korean media. In addition to the visual influence in films and dramas, the spread of Korean food culture in Indonesia is supported by the South Korean government's gastrodiplomacy policy. According to (Jin, 2016), South Korea utilizes pop culture, including K-drama and K-pop, to introduce its traditional culinary culture. Korean food has become a tool of cultural diplomacy, strengthening South Korea's positive image. In Indonesia, this is reflected in the growing number of Korean restaurants that have emerged, offering flavors tailored to local tastes. (Kim & Lee, 2017).

The portrayal of food in Korean films and dramas is not only for visual appeal, but also for shaping global cultural perceptions. Appealing food in popular narratives helps Korean culture establish culinary standards that are adopted by international audiences, including those in Indonesia. Korean cultural consumption encompasses music, drama, lifestyle, and food, which become cultural identities transmitted through popular media. In 2016, growing interest in Korean dramas featuring foods like kimchi, bibimbap, and Ramyeon led Indonesian consumers to seek similar dining experiences. Korean restaurants in Indonesia began modifying their food presentation methods to resemble those depicted in Korean media, including the use of metal cutlery and the presentation of Banchan (Banchan). This phenomenon demonstrates the influence of South Korean popular media on culinary practices abroad.

The success of South Korea's gastrodiplomacy in Indonesia stems from the abundance of Korean restaurants and the adoption of Korean culinary culture by Indonesians. South Korea uses media such as dramas and music to introduce traditional foods, which Indonesians then adapt. This illustrates the impact of popular culture on culinary preferences and the emergence of new business opportunities in other countries. However, Korean food in Indonesia also faces challenges, including differences in taste, limited access to authentic ingredients, and the need for halal certification. To address these challenges, Korean culinary businesses in Indonesia need to adapt by considering local preferences and ensuring that their products align with Indonesian cultural and religious values.

Based on the previous explanation, Indonesia has experienced a significant increase in the consumption of South Korean popular culture, especially films and television dramas, since the early 2010s. A clear impact of this is the wide variety of South Korean restaurant food in Indonesia, influenced by the visualization of Korean food in dramas and films, which influences Indonesian consumers' expectations of South Korean cuisine. In 2016, an increasing number of South Korean restaurants created variations of food from South Korean media, showing food in visual media as an effective cultural and lifestyle promotion tool. This trend is not only happening in Indonesia, but also globally. Data from the Korean Foundation for International Cultural Exchange and Statista (2025) shows that the popularity of Korean cuisine in the world increased from 42.7% in 2017 to 53.7% in 2024. This shows that K-food has become part of a global identity associated with modernity, health, and the aesthetics of South Korean media. The visualization of food in K-dramas and K-films has created a cultural desire, where viewers not only want to imitate Korean clothing styles or music, but also Korean eating habits and types of food (Korean, 2025).

(Korean, 2025)

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In this context, Korean food has become a symbol rich in cultural meaning. (Kwon, 2023) explains that Korean food is not only delicious but also reflects the philosophy of balance and harmony. This shapes Indonesian consumers' perceptions that Korean food is healthy and has authentic traditions. The growing interest in Korean restaurants in Indonesia reflects the interaction between media, culture, and culinary tastes. The emergence of Korean food variants in Indonesian restaurants is influenced by local adaptation strategies aimed at making K-food more acceptable to consumers. Many restaurants adjust their spiciness levels, use halal meat, and maintain their presentations to suit local preferences. This process strengthens K-food's position as a global cultural product that is both flexible and adaptable to local tastes without compromising its authentic identity.

Gastrodiplomacy is a form of public diplomacy that uses food to create a positive image of a country and strengthen international relations through culinary programs. Food is considered an effective way to convey national culture and identity to the international community. In the Indonesian context, the increase in consumption of South Korean films and dramas since the early 2010s has increased public interest in Korean culture, including culinary arts. The presentation of food in Korean media has influenced the expectations of Indonesian consumers, resulting in many Korean restaurants displaying presentations similar to those depicted in Korean media. (Cowan, 2022).

Among the various countries that utilize the cultural industry to expand their influence in Indonesia, the author notes that South Korea plays a significant role in the food sector, particularly through the expansion of Korean food businesses in the Indonesian market. This strategy is part of gastrodiplomacy, where South Korea leverages the popularity of pop culture such as K-pop and Korean dramas to encourage the acceptance of its traditional foods in various countries, including Indonesia. This strategy is part of gastrodiplomacy, where South Korea leverages the popularity of pop culture, such as K-pop and South Korean dramas, to increase the acceptance of its traditional foods in various countries, including Indonesia. South Korean food is present not only as imported products, but also through the development of restaurants in major cities. According to a Kompas report, Indonesia is now one of the most significant markets for South Korean food businesses. Several well-known brands, including BBQ, Ojju, and Mukbang, have established numerous branches across various regions of Indonesia. In addition, the Korea Agro-Fisheries & Food Trade Corporation (at Center of Jakarta) noted that the increasing interest of the Indonesian public in South Korean food has also encouraged exports of South Korean food ingredients to the Indonesian market. Therefore, the author chose South Korea as the country to be studied in depth in this research.

With the increasing number of South Korean film enthusiasts in Indonesia, there has been an increase in interest in South Korean culture, including culinary arts. This phenomenon is evident in the increasing number of South Korean restaurants and the popularity of foods such as Kimchi, Tteokbokki, and Bibimbap. Exposure to South Korean culinary culture through dramas and films has shaped new preferences in food consumption in Indonesia. Therefore, the question that will be raised in this paper is: How did South Korean films influence the variety of foods in Indonesia in 2016? The author uses the theory of gastrodiplomacy to examine how food is used as a means of spreading culture and creating interest between nations. (S. Rockower, 2012)

II. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

This study examines previous research on the influx of South Korean culture into Indonesia through popular media, particularly Korean films and dramas. This popular culture, driven by globalization, has given rise to cross-cultural consumption trends, including in the culinary aspect. According to Mutahir, Nasrullah, and Arif (2023), the popularity of Korean films and dramas has contributed to an increasing interest in Korean food among Indonesians, which has been adapted to the local context through the process of glocalization. Popular culture, known as the "Korean Wave," has spread widely to various countries, including Indonesia, and has influenced lifestyles and consumption patterns across these countries. The issue of transnationalism has impacted the domestic industry, where Indonesian food producers have created Korean-style instant food products as an adaptation to global tastes influenced by Korean Pop Music and Korean Dramas.

This phenomenon has increased Indonesian society's interest in South Korean products, including culinary and entertainment offerings, reflecting the significant influence of globalization and cross-cultural interactions between countries. Along with the increasing popularity of Korean dramas and music (Korean Pop Music), culinary consumption in South Korea in Indonesia has also increased, with products such as (Tteokbokki, Mandu, Kimchi, Soju), which are now widely found. This finding aligns with the results of Ormond and Sulianti (2014) and King (2015). This indicates that social, cultural aspects, as well as symbolic and virtual interactions, play a significant role in shaping transnational phenomena and cultural mobility across national borders, involving the adaptation of popular culture in the recipient country. The phenomenon of increasing interest in Indonesian people towards South Korean cuisine since 2016 has had a significant impact on the "Korean Wave" in food consumption patterns. Research by Putri et al. (2024) explains that the "Korean Wave" influences Korean food purchasing decisions in Jakarta. Research by Safitri (2021) analyzes South Korea's implementation of gastrodiplomacy through the promotion of halal food in Indonesia from 2015 to 2016. This research demonstrates that success in increasing Indonesian people's interest in Korean food is achieved by making it similar to the local taste image.

South Korea collaborates with halal certification agencies, organizes South Korean food exhibitions, and produces the drama "Lunch" to build a positive image of South Korean culture. This helps expand the Korean halal market and strengthens national

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branding and diplomatic relations. (p. Safitri 2021). This strategy aligns with South Korea's promotion of Hansik, or traditional Korean cuisine, as a global cultural heritage, emphasizing its culinary aspects, historical and symbolic values as part of Korean cultural diplomacy on the international stage. (pp. Kim, 2017).

The five articles above provide the author with important insights into how South Korea, particularly through films and dramas, functions not only as entertainment but also as a vehicle for disseminating transnational popular culture, influencing culinary consumption patterns in Indonesia. Cultural aspects significantly influence public tastes, while economic and political aspects are also crucial as they relate to Korea's soft power strategy through halal gastrodiplomacy. This phenomenon illustrates how globalization, popular media, and local cultural adaptations enhance South Korea's national image and expand its culinary industry in Muslim-majority countries, such as Indonesia.

Furthermore, the author gained insight from Candy's (2021) research which explained that the "Korean Wave" influenced not only entertainment but also food consumption patterns in Indonesia. The popularity of Korean culture, particularly among groups like BTS and Korean Dramas, has led people to prefer Korean food products such as Ramyeon, Kimchi, and Tteokbokki. This study also examined the collaboration between McDonald's and the idol group BTS through the BTS Meal which triggered long queues and mass euphoria in Indonesia. This illustrates the influence of popular culture on shaping consumer behavior. (Erycha Budiana Sari, 2023) Research by Yulianan and Nugaraha (2021) shows that the "Korean Wave," especially Korean Pop, influences the consumer behavior of Bekasi students. This quantitative study involved 90 respondents and found a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) from the calculated and tabulated values, explaining 86.3% of the variation in the consumer behavior of fans.

This Trend not only spreads South Korean culture through the media, but North Korean culinary culture has also become an export commodity in the context of cultural diplomacy and political economy. A study by (p. Opiumwar 2020) in Indonesia and North Korea shows that North Korean restaurants abroad, such as Yanbian, China, serve as a source of foreign exchange and showcase culinary specialties like sinseollo and Taedonggang beer. Although limited by political policy, this cultural export showcases Korean food. (p. Opiumwar 2020).

Meanwhile, in South Korea, cuisine is also a key element of the Korean Wave, shaping global tastes and lifestyles. In Indonesia, the Korean cultural wave has not only created fans but also transformed people's consumption habits, including food choices, hangout spots, and lifestyles. According to the author (Tobing, 2020), the "Korean Wave" has evolved into a comprehensive lifestyle that influences consumer choices regarding food, beauty, and cultural values adopted through popular media. South Korea's soft power is further strengthened through its culinary arts, dramas, popular music (K-pop), and the role of entertainment industries, such as SM Entertainment, in introducing South Korean culture to the world. Furthermore, the influence of Korean dramas has been shown to drive interest in Korean food consumption among young Indonesians. (Rahmayanti et al. 2022) explained a significant correlation between watching South Korean dramas and interest in purchasing Korean food among university students in Surabaya. Korean dramas are the primary driver of increased consumption of foods such as tteokbokki and ramyeon. These findings suggest that popular media influences culinary consumption preferences and reinforces the role of South Korean dramas.

South Korea's positive image as a developed and clean nation strengthens its cultural appeal, including its culinary offerings. According to Oppenheim (2021), the concept of "Korean quality" in labor migration in Nepal portrays Korea as a symbol of high quality and progress. This image shapes migrant workers' expectations and global perceptions of Korean products, including food. In Indonesia, Korean food has become part of a modern lifestyle associated with the values of "Korean quality." Thus, interest in Korean food is driven not only by media exposure but also by its inherent cultural symbolism.

According to research and data analysis by Syyaf (2023), Indonesian interest in Korean cuisine is growing, particularly in halal-certified products like ramyeon, kimchi, and tteokbokki. This confirms that the success of Korean culinary expansion in Indonesia is determined not only by cultural exposure through popular media like Korean dramas but also by the ability of Korean businesses to understand and meet the needs and values of local communities, particularly Muslim consumers in Indonesia.

Furthermore, research by Asy'ari (2024) explains that South Korean gastrodiplomacy serves as a means of spreading culture through food, creating culinary business opportunities in Indonesia. By capitalizing on the "Korean Wave," South Korea is attracting Indonesian consumers to its cuisine. This is evident in the numerous Korean restaurants and food outlets in major Indonesian cities. Adapting to local values and customs is also crucial for maintaining the sustainability of this expansion.

Furthermore, (Fidela, 2024) explains that South Korea's gastrodiplomacy significantly helped increase Korean food exports to Indonesia between 2014 and 2023, despite the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. This strategy also strengthened the country's image and expanded the market for Korean food products, and was supported by Indonesian interest in Korean cuisine. (Maksum, 2024) explains that South Korea used gastrodiplomacy to protect and expand national interests during the COVID-19 pandemic by increasing halal food exports to Indonesia.

(Sabarguna, 2023) explains that the popularity of Korean culture, known as the Korean Wave, increased Indonesian interest in Korean instant foods. This phenomenon encouraged the consumption of imported products and inspired local producers to create Korean versions of instant foods. His research also explains that lifestyle changes during the COVID-19 pandemic strengthened the trend of consuming Korean cultural products, including food, opening new business opportunities. Indonesian producers adapted to local ingredients and flavors while maintaining the appeal of Korean cuisine as a promotional strategy.

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According to Rheya (2024), more than 700,000 tweets on the platform X were analyzed to determine Indonesian public opinion on South Korean culture. This study explains that the Korean Wave generates diverse public reactions, both enthusiastic support and critical rejection. Using a CNN-based deep learning algorithm, this study provides accurate quantitative insights into public responses to Korean pop music, drama, food, and Korean lifestyle. These findings highlight the critical role of social media in reflecting and shaping public opinion on foreign cultural phenomena such as Hallyu. Furthermore, Rahmawati (2023) explains that Korean dramas, as part of South Korean popular culture, attract the attention of the global community, including Indonesia. The study demonstrates that watching Korean dramas on television, such as RCTI, shapes new cultural perceptions and routines among Indonesian teenagers.

Enthusiasm for Korean dramas also increases interest in Korean products, including food, technology, fashion, and tourism. This demonstrates South Korea's success in spreading its national identity through government-supported cultural strategies. Based on various previous studies, the author discusses the influence of South Korean films on food presentation in Indonesia in 2016 using gastrodiplomacy theory as an analytical framework.

III. METHOD

This study examines the dynamics of South Korean gastrodiplomacy in Indonesia, focusing on the roles of South Korean restaurants, food festivals, and coalitions in building South Korean cultural influence through the culinary arts. This study employs a qualitative method with a deductive approach, utilizing the theories of gastrodiplomacy and cultural diplomacy as the primary analytical framework. Qualitative research methods are chosen to understand complex social phenomena through the collection of descriptive data such as words, narratives, and documents.

This paper utilizes secondary data, comprising official sources such as government reports, documents from the South Korean Embassy in Indonesia, as well as journal articles and news articles on Korean gastrodiplomacy in Indonesia. Additionally, additional information was obtained from the official websites of relevant government agencies and cultural institutions. The data were analyzed categorically, referring to the theoretical framework of gastrodiplomacy. This study also employed triangulation of data sources to enhance the validity and reliability of the findings by comparing data from multiple sources.

This study aims to analyze the dynamics of South Korean gastrodiplomacy in Indonesia and ensure the accuracy of the data presented. The study is divided into three chapters. The first chapter discusses the background, problem formulation, gastrodiplomacy theory, literature review, and research methods. The second chapter examines the role of Korean restaurants and food festivals, as well as the response of the Indonesian public. The third chapter presents the author's conclusions and reflections on the challenges of Korean gastrodiplomacy in Indonesia.

IV. RESULT

This section explains the concept of South Korean gastrodiplomacy, which is comprised of four sub-chapters based on four main variables. The first sub-chapter examines the impact of Korean films and dramas on shaping the variety of Korean food adapted in Indonesia through their visually appealing culinary presentations. The second sub-chapter analyzes the role of Korean restaurants in Indonesia in representing Korean food culture and adapting to local values. The third sub-chapter explains the role of Korean food festivals as a means of cultural diplomacy. The final sub-chapter examines coalition building between South Korean cultural institutions in Indonesia.

A. *The Influence of Korean Films and Dramas on South Korean Food Variations in Indonesia*

According to Wachyuni (2023), traditional food in Korean dramas serves not only aesthetic or narrative purposes, but also as a cultural promotional tool. This indicates that entertainment media serve as an attractive soft-selling tool to influence consumer behavior and tourism preferences, particularly in culinary tourism. Food visualizations build curiosity and emotional experiences, encouraging viewers to want to "experience" Korean culture. Korean dramas have become a significant means of shaping positive perceptions of Korean culture. The increasing interest of Indonesians in South Korean culture, especially through drama broadcasts,

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reflects the globalization of culture and the motivation for culinary tourism to Korea. Research (Wachyuni, 2023) indicates that traditional South Korean food featured in dramas serves as a significant attraction for Indonesian tourists. Scenes featuring food in films/dramas, such as Tteokbokki, Ramyeon, Kimchi, Bibimbap, Kimbap, Samgyeopsal, Japchae, Jjajangmyeon, as well as snacks like Korean Corn Dogs and Hotteok, provide audiences with an interest in enjoying these foods in their country of origin as part of an authentic tourism experience.

(Koreobo, 2025)

(Kompas.com, 2025)

The two photos above show variations of South Korean food featured in the drama. The drama introduces a variation of South Korean food, bibimbap. The authentic visuals can pique viewers' curiosity and make them want to try it.

B. The role of Korean restaurants in Indonesia in presenting Korean food culture.

South Korean restaurants in Indonesia are not just for dining, but also a reflection of Korea's rich culture. With interior designs reminiscent of traditional Korean houses (hanok), distinctive cutlery, and authentic dishes, such as kimchi and bulgogi, these restaurants offer a dining experience similar to that of South Korea and maintain the authenticity of South Korean culture. (Kusbiantoro, 2015). To be accepted by Indonesians with diverse cultural backgrounds and taste preferences, Korean restaurants make various adaptations to local values.

One example is adjusting the level of spiciness and the use of local ingredients in Korean dishes. For example, gochujang sauce, the main seasoning in tteokbokki, is replaced with a local chili sauce that is more in line with Indonesian tastes and meets halal standards. (Mutahir, 2024). Beyond mere consumption, South Korean restaurants also create new economic opportunities and reinforce South Korean culture within urban Indonesian communities. This strategy involves visual promotion through Korean dramas, social media, and K-Food Fair events. Restaurants serve as a bridge between media culture and real-life experiences, promoting a Korean national image and identity that is accepted by Indonesians. (Asy'ari, 2024)

C. South Korean Food Festival Cultural Diplomacy, and Cultural Diplomacy Relations Means

Food festivals such as the K-Food Festival, Hansik Day, and culinary collaborations with local restaurants in various countries, including Indonesia, are part of the Korean cultural dissemination project called the "Korean Wave." Food serves as a medium to build positive perceptions of its country of origin and reflects the history, identity, and social values of the community (Rockower, 2012). Through food festivals, South Korea creates an informal yet impactful space for cultural communication. Interaction with South Korean food helps people learn about other cultures, such as language and traditions. These encounters enhance cross-cultural understanding and foster interest in the host country, as demonstrated in a study (Choi, 2020) on public perceptions of South Korea through culinary arts. In Indonesia, Korean food festivals function as public diplomacy, strengthening bilateral relations and becoming a venue for participatory cultural exchange. These activities involve embassies, Korean communities, and local communities, making cultural diplomacy more open. According to (Sung, 2014), Korean culinary culture helps shape the national image in the eyes of the global public. Thus, South Korean food festivals are more than just culinary promotion. This is a form of cultural diplomacy that builds emotional connections, expands cultural influence, and strengthens diplomatic relations. (Kim, 2013)

D. Coalition Building Between South Korean Cultural Institutions in Indonesia

According to (Ade, 2012), South Korea's nation branding through South Korean Popular Culture in Indonesia aims to introduce the culture and serve as a diplomatic tool to build a positive image of the country. Through institutions such as the Presidential Council on Nation Branding and the Korean Creative Content Agency (KOCCA), South Korea implements a branding strategy by distributing Korean music, films, and dramas. Through dramas and films, Indonesians are exposed to various attractive images of Korean food. Dishes like tteobokki, kimchi, bulgogi, and bibimbap not only complement the story but also capture the audience's attention and arouse curiosity. This makes Korean food popular, especially among teenagers and young adults.

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This trend has encouraged the emergence of various Korean restaurants in major Indonesian cities in the years since 2016, as well as the increased availability of Korean food products in local supermarkets. Consumers not only want to watch Korean films but also experience the culture they see on screen, which is manifested in their food consumption practices. South Korean films have had a significant impact on expanding the variety of foods consumed by Indonesians and have become an important channel for introducing and popularizing Korean cuisine in Indonesia.

According to Wachyuni (2023), the visualization of food in South Korean dramas significantly influences the motivation of Indonesian tourists to visit South Korea. However, before the actual travel phase, one of the reactions of Indonesian viewers is the desire to experience South Korean culture through food. Post-2016, there has been a significant increase in the opening of South Korean restaurants in major cities such as Jakarta, Bandung, Surabaya, and Yogyakarta. In addition to modern restaurants, small Korean drama-themed stalls have emerged with a variety of menus inspired by popular scenes from the films. South Korean food products, such as ramyeon, gochujang sauce, and typical South Korean snacks, are also increasingly available in supermarkets and minimarkets.

This demonstrates South Korea as an effective platform for introducing and marketing South Korean culinary culture. This trend is not only a consumption trend but also reflects a shift in Indonesian culinary culture. Indonesians are now beginning to adopt elements of East Asian cuisine, particularly South Korean cuisine. These films serve as cultural windows, helping people access and reshape food preferences, but also fostering new lifestyles and cultural identities among consumers.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn from this analysis are as follows. First, the visualization of food in Korean films and dramas has served as an effective cultural promotion tool. Scenes featuring traditional Korean dishes such as kimchi, bibimbap, bulgogi, and ramyeon shape consumer expectations and drive demand for similar foods in Indonesia, particularly through restaurants and cultural festivals. Second, the involvement of various actors, including the South Korean government, culinary businesses, entertainment media, and local communities in Indonesia, demonstrates that the spread of South Korean culinary culture is carried out through a multi-actor approach. This strengthens the gastrodiplomacy network, which is not dependent on a single institution but is collaborative and complex. Third, the lack of a single dominant force in the cultural adaptation process has led to variations in the presentation of Korean food in Indonesia. Adaptation to local values reflects ongoing cultural negotiations between the two parties. Fourth, South Korea's gastrodiplomacy strategy demonstrates that when popular culture is integrated through media, food, and cross-sectoral collaboration, a mutually beneficial cultural interdependence is created. South Korea expands its cultural market, while Indonesia benefits in the form of business opportunities, culinary diversification, and new cultural experiences. Fifth, this cultural relationship makes a complete halt to the spread of Korean culinary culture highly unlikely. Instead, this relationship will be maintained and even strengthened through symbolic negotiations and future economic-cultural collaboration. Thus, this study answers the question of how South Korean films influence the diversity of Indonesian food. Through a structured and sustained gastrodiplomacy strategy, South Korea has successfully introduced and embedded its food culture into the Indonesian culinary landscape, transforming food not only as a consumption necessity but also as an effective medium for cultural communication.

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